

Adsorptive removal of methylene blue dye from simulated wastewater using shale : Experiment and modelling

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Abstract : Water pollution due to presence of toxic dye becomes a threat to aquatic biota. Methylene blue, a toxic dye, which is used in huge amount in textile industry, has been chosen as model pollutant in the present study. Shale, a mine waste, collected from Sonepurbazari coalfield, West Bengal, India, has been used to remove methylene blue dye from its simulated solution. Both Native Sonepurbazari Shale (NSS) and Heat Treated Sonepurbazari Shale (HTSS) have been used to remove methylene blue and NSS has been found to be more effective than its heat treated form. Characterization of shale samples have been done before and after treatment with methylene blue. The operating parameters such as initial concentration (100–200 mg/L), adsorbent dose (4–12 g/L), size of adsorbent (90–212 μ) and temperature (25–35°C) have been varied in prescribed manner. PSOM and Langmuir adsorption isotherm model have been found to be best to analyse kinetic and equilibrium data, respectively. An empirical model is developed to predict the interactive effect of five input variables namely initial concentration of methylene blue dye, adsorbent dose, particle size, temperature, and time with one output variable namely percentage removal of methylene blue.

Keywords : Methylene blue, shale, adsorption, kinetic study, desorption, modelling.

Introduction

Dyes are extensively used in numerous industries like textile, rubber, paper, food and plastics¹. The effluents coming from such industries are extremely coloured and the contamination of these wastes into receiving waters cause severe problems to the aquatic life and environment². The textile industry plays a vital role in the economic development of many countries in the world³. Since huge amount of water is used in the dyeing process, textile industry is one of the largest producers of liquid effluent pollutants⁴. The textile industry effluent typically contains 0.6–0.8 g/L of dye, but the pollution is mainly due to the stability of the dyes⁵. Methylene blue, a toxic dye, is commonly used for dyeing cotton, wood and silk⁶. It has adverse effect on the human being such as vomiting, nausea, diarrhoea, etc.⁷. Therefore, removal of methylene blue from wastewater is very essential from environment point of view. Various physico-

chemical approaches have been made to remove the dyes from textile effluent like chemical precipitation, nano-filtration⁸, and coagulation-flocculation⁹. However, most of these technologies are having some inherent problems like not being effective in colour removal, generation of secondary sludge, high cost of treatment, etc.⁵. In contrast, adsorption, being a simple technique, effective and economic can be used for removal of dye¹⁰. Furthermore, adsorption works at ambient pressure and temperature. Many studies have been carried out to utilize agricultural by-products as low cost adsorbent material in wastewater treatment, for example rice husk and saw dust¹, oil palm fibre¹¹, hazelnut shell², palm bark and eucalyptus¹², coconut shell¹³, banana and orange peels¹⁴. The problems associated with agricultural by-products are less removal when used in its native form, dependence on seasonal variation, etc. However, adsorbents prepared by carbonizing such waste materials have been utilised

for dye removal since they have good adsorption capacity¹⁵. However, the process of preparation of activated carbon comprising of two steps namely carbonization at high temperature and physical or chemical activation using steam or chemicals is tedious and incurs cost to the system⁴. Therefore, researches are now directing towards the searching of no-cost material having excellent adsorption capability. Shale is a fine grained sedimentary rock commonly associated with coal-seam in the coalfield¹⁶. Stripping off overburdens to produce coal often generates huge quantity of solid wastes, in which the shale is the principal constituent. Shale is composed of different minerals like kaolinite, montmorillonite, etc. and its colour is grey. The structural constituent of shale is responsible for its adsorption properties. Hydroxyl groups, present at the surface, results in ion-exchange property of the shale or clay particle¹⁷. In the present study, both native and heat treated shale has been used separately to remediate methylene blue from simulated solution. Characterization of shale preliminary proves the adsorption of dye onto shale. The utilization of shale for removal of dye from wastewater serves two purposes. Firstly, the wastewater will be reclaimed in environmental friendly and cost-effective manner and secondly, utilization of shale for removal of pollutant will solve the problem of solid waste disposal.

Results and discussion

Characterization of shale :

Physico chemical characterization of both NSS and HTSS have been done by evaluating their bulk density, solid density, moisture content, total organic carbon, pH_{zpc} , BET surface area. 90 μ particle size has been used for both the cases. Table 1 shows the values of those parameters.

From Table 1, it is seen that solid density of shale samples are quite high. The carbonaceous adsorbent such as agricultural residue (bagasse) has solid density 0.12 g/cc¹⁸, whereas for clay minerals such as diatomite and sepiolite have solid densities of 1.74 g/cc¹⁷ and 2.5 g/cc¹⁹, respectively. Being a sedimentary rock, higher solid density of NSS (2.19 g/cc)

Table 1. Characterization of NSS and HTSS

Properties	Values	
	NSS	HTSS
Bulk density (g/cm ³)	1.25	0.66
Solid density (g/cm ³)	2.19	2.49
Moisture content (%)	5.41	0.009
TOC (%)	0.87	1.76
BET surface area (m ² /g)	15.35	3.78
pH_{zpc}	7.5	8.1

and HTSS (2.49 g/cc) are expected²⁰. Furthermore, due to evolution of water of hydration, volatile matter, etc., during heating of NSS at 550°C, HTSS becomes more compact than NSS and higher solid density in case of HTSS is observed. For the same reason, moisture content of HTSS (0.009%) has been found to be much lower than its native form (5.41%). Since the native shale contains hydroxyl groups in large amount¹⁸, due to heating at higher temperature, these inorganic groups are emitted and organic carbon content increases in HTSS (1.76%) as observed in Table 1. Again, due to the evolution of occluded gases and moisture during heating for preparation of HTSS, the shale becomes more compact and lower BET surface area is observed for HTSS (3.78 m²/g) than its native form (15.35 m²/g). pH_{zpc} of NSS and HTSS have been found to be 7.5 and 8.1, respectively. pH_{zpc} signifies the surface charge of the adsorbent. The surface of adsorbent will become positive if the operational pH is less than pH_{zpc} and vice versa²¹. Fig. 1a and Fig. 1b shows the scanning electron microscopy images of both NSS and NSS loaded with MB, respectively. The figures are almost identical, however, a smoothening effect is seen after loading of MB on NSS.

Fig. 2a and Fig. 2b shows the EDAX spectra of NSS both before and after treatment with methylene blue. Fig. 2a shows the composition of different elements present in shale before treatment with methylene blue. Maximum amount of oxygen (44.28%) has been found in the sample followed by carbon, sodium, magnesium, silicon, aluminium, iron and potassium. Fig. 2b shows the composition of different elements present in shale after adsorption of methyl-

Fig. 1a. Scanning Electron Micrograph of NSS before treatment with MB.

Fig. 1b. Scanning Electron Micrograph of NSS after treatment with MB.

ene blue. Maximum amount of oxygen (52.41%) has been found in the sample followed by carbon, manganese, sodium, magnesium, aluminium, silicon, potassium, calcium and iron, respectively. Since methylene blue dye is an organic compound containing very common basic elements such as carbon, nitrogen, hydrogen, etc., EDAX image of MB loaded NSS have not showed any distinct proof of adsorption of dye.

Fig. 3a and Fig. 3b represent the FTIR spectra of native shale and shale after adsorption of methylene blue, respectively. The stretching frequencies (cm^{-1}) of the bonds for NSS have been found as follows : 628, 1035, 3414 and 3621 cm^{-1} representing $-\text{C}\equiv\text{C}-\text{H}$: C-H bend, C-O stretch, H-O-H bond, and $-\text{O}-\text{H}$ (strong and sharp) bonds, respectively. Whereas in methylene blue adsorbed shale, the peaks have been found as follows 625, 1032, 1423, 1603 and 3414 cm^{-1} representing $-\text{C}\equiv\text{C}-\text{H}$: C-H bend, C-O stretch, C-C stretch (in-ring), N-H bond, and H-O-H bond (H-bonded) respectively. The elimination of $-\text{O}-\text{H}$ (strong and sharp) bonds in MB loaded shale may be due to the involvement of such group in adsorption of MB. The presence of N-H bond gives initial proof of adsorption of dye onto shale.

Fig. 2a. EDAX spectra of NSS before treatment with MB.

Fig. 2b. EDAX spectra of NSS after treatment with MB.

Kinetics of removal of dye using shale :

Effect of initial MB concentration :

Kinetics of removal of MB dye has been done using NSS and HTSS with initial concentration as varying parameter as shown in Fig. 4a and Fig. 4b. Adsorbent dose, temperature, and particle size of shale have been maintained constant at 4 g/L, 30°C, and

90 μ , respectively. Major removal of MB has been reached within 4 min. After 6 min of contact, no variation in dye removal has been observed. Thus, each experiment has been carried out for 10 min during batch study. The percentage removal of dye decreases from 93.89% to 88.95% using NSS, whereas, in case of HTSS, the percentage removal decreases from 83.02% to 79.37% with an increase in initial

Fig. 3a. FTIR spectra of NSS before treatment with MB.

Fig. 3b. FTIR spectra of NSS after treatment with MB.

concentration of dye from 100 mg/L to 200 mg/L (Fig. 4a and Fig. 4b). The decrease in BET surface area in case of HTSS may be the reason for less removal of dye. Demirbas *et al.*²² reported the similar observation that with increase in concentration of dye, the percent removal decreased. Similar observations were made by several scientists such as adsorption of malachite green using treated sawdust²³, adsorption of methylene blue using treated Indian Rosewood sawdust²⁴, adsorption of methylene blue onto activated lignin-chitosan extruded blends²⁵. The probable mechanism of dye removal has been showed in

Fig. 5. The lone pair of oxygen of hydroxyl group, as present in the crystal lattice of shale, attacks the positive centre of methylene blue dye and replaces chloride ion and thus, one molecule of hydrogen chloride has been formed^{20,26}. Since the migration of charge has been restricted after such reaction, the decolourization of dye takes place (Fig. 5).

Effect of adsorbent dose :

The influence of adsorbent dose for removal of methylene blue dye is shown in Fig. 6a and Fig. 6b, when NSS and HTSS have been used as adsorbent, respectively. Initial concentration, temperature and

Fig. 4a. Removal of MB using NSS at various initial concentrations of dye.

Fig. 4b. Removal of MB using HTSS at various initial concentrations of dye.

Fig. 5. Mechanism of binding methylene blue dye with shale.

particle size have been kept constant at 100 μ m, 30°C and 90 μ m, respectively. Maximum removal of MB has been observed at 100 mg/L and 12 g/L of adsorbent with 90 μ m size at 30°C. The percentage removal of dye increases with increase in adsorbent dose from 4 to 12 g/L. As adsorption is surface phenomenon, the increase in adsorbent dose means availability of more surface for adsorption. With increase in doses from 4 to 12 g/L, the percentage removal of MB increases from 93.89 to 98.66% and from 83.02 to 88.35% when NSS and HTSS have been used as adsorbent, respectively (Fig. 6a and Fig. 6b). Demirbas *et al.*²² observed that with increase in adsorbent dose the percentage removal of dye increased. Similar observations were reported by several scientists. Removal of methylene blue onto teak tree bark powder²⁷, removal of astrazon blue dye onto sepiolite, fly ash, and apricot shell activated carbon²⁸⁻³⁰ are some of them.

Effect of particle size :

For assessing the effect of particle size on the adsorption of MB dye, the particle size has been varied from 90 μ m to 212 μ m, and other parameters have been kept constant viz. initial concentration (100 mg/L), dose of adsorbent (4 g/L), and temperature (30°C), respectively. The removal efficacy of shale has been found to be maximum for 90 μ m particle and minimum for 212 μ m particle. With decrease in particle size of the shale from 212–90 μ m, the percentage removal of MB increases from 87.48 to 93.89% with NSS and from 77.80 to 83.02% with HTSS as shown in Fig. 7a and Fig. 7b, respectively. The higher removal of dye at lower particle size is obvious since smaller

Fig. 6a. Removal of MB using NSS at various adsorbent doses of shale.

Fig. 6b. Removal of MB using HTSS at various adsorbent doses of shale.

particle has more surface area^{2,27}.

Effect of temperature :

The kinetic study of removal of MB dye has been done by varying the temperature from 25°C to 35°C, other parameters have been maintained constant like initial concentration, particle size and adsorbent dose as 100 mg/L, 90 μ m and 4 g/L, respectively. While temperature rises from 25–35°C, the percentage removal increases from 93 to 95.91% with NSS (Fig. 8a) and from 80.19 to 88.90% with HTSS (Fig. 8b). From the data it is clear that the removal is almost independent on the temperature under the present range studied. It is evident that enhanced temperature of dye solution facilitates the diffusional rate of adsor-

Fig. 7a. Removal of MB using NSS by varying the particle sizes of the shale.

Fig. 8a. Removal of MB using NSS at various temperatures.

Fig. 7b. Removal of MB using HTSS by varying the particle sizes of the shale.

Fig. 8b. Removal of MB using HTSS at various temperatures.

bate molecules across the boundary layer as well as through the pores of the adsorbent molecules, which eventually leads to the higher percentage removal of dye³¹. In addition, variation of temperature will result in change in the equilibrium capacity of the adsorbent for a particular adsorbate². Jia *et al.*³², showed that the percentage removal of dye increases with increase in temperature.

Analysis of kinetic and equilibrium data :

The data obtained by varying the initial concentration and dose of shale have been fitted to different kinetic models namely, Morris-Weber model, pseudo-first order Lagergren model and McKay Ho pseudo-

second order model individually. Morris-Weber model is diffusional rate controlled and can be expressed as follows^{22,33,34} :

$$q_t = K'_m t^{1/2} \tag{5}$$

where q_t = concentration of adsorbate in solid phase at any time t (mg/g), K'_m = Morris-Weber rate constant (mg/g/min^{-1/2}).

Both Lagergren first order model and pseudo-second order model are reaction rate based models^{6,22}. The Lagergren first order model can be expressed as follows :

$$\log (q_e - q_t) = \log q_e - \frac{K'_L t}{2.303} \tag{6}$$

where K'_L = Lagergren rate constant (min^{-1}), q_e = concentration of adsorbate in solid phase at equilibrium with that in liquid phase (mg/g).

McKay Ho model (PSOM) assumes that the removal of dye is controlled by reaction rate and it is proportional to square of concentration of dye in solid phase³⁴. The integral form of rate equation is as follows :

$$\frac{t}{q_t} = \frac{1}{K'_p q_e^2} + \frac{t}{q_e} \quad (7)$$

where K'_p = McKay Ho rate constant (g mg/min).

The kinetic data have been seen to be analysed best by pseudo-second order model as evident from the high values of correlation coefficient. The values of kinetic parameters are shown in Table 2. The equilibrium study has been done with only NSS. Equilibrium study has been performed at four different temperatures viz. 25°C, 30°C, 35°C and 40°C. Two

equilibrium models such as Langmuir and Freundlich adsorption isotherm models have been used individually to analyse equilibrium concentrations. Langmuir adsorption model has been analysed best to represent the equilibrium concentrations. The values of equilibrium parameters and correlation co-efficients have been shown in Table 3.

Desorption study :

Desorption study has been performed with spent shale at three different pH conditions (3.7, 7.5 and 10) individually. Maximum desorption (27.8%) is observed at pH 3.7. Vaz *et al.* (2017)³⁵ observed maximum desorption under strong acidic condition. From the structure of methylene blue, it is seen that MB is cationic in nature. The negative charge of shale attracts MB and thereby, excellent adsorption is achieved during kinetic study at pH 7. However, at lower pH, the hydrogen ion competes with dye and thereby, desorption occurs more at low pH.

Table 2. The values of kinetic parameters

Kinetic models	C=100	C=150	C=200	D=8 g/L	D=12 g/L
	mg/L	mg/L	mg/L	C=100	C=100
Morris-Weber model $q_t = K'_m t^{1/2}$	$K'_m = 0.001$ $R^2 = 0.790$	$K'_m = 0.065$ $R^2 = 0.908$	$K'_m = 0.075$ $R^2 = 0.836$	$K'_m = 0.038$ $R^2 = 0.973$	$K'_m = 0.052$ $R^2 = 0.984$
Lagergren model $\log(q_e - q_t) = \log q_e - \frac{K'_L t}{2.303}$	$K'_L = 0.039$ $R^2 = 0.926$	$K'_L = 0.035$ $R^2 = 0.758$	$K'_L = 0.069$ $R^2 = 0.970$	$K'_L = 0.044$ $R^2 = 0.925$	$K'_L = 0.072$ $R^2 = 0.949$
PSOM $\frac{t}{q_t} = \frac{1}{K'_p q_e^2} + \frac{t}{q_e}$	$K'_p = 0.70$ $R^2 = 1.0$	$K'_p = 0.409$ $R^2 = 1.0$	$K'_p = 0.186$ $R^2 = 1.0$	$K'_p = 0.357$ $R^2 = 1.0$	$K'_p = 0.297$ $R^2 = 1.0$

Table 3. The values of equilibrium parameters and correlation co-efficient

Adsorption isotherm	Temperature (°C)			
	25	30	35	40
Langmuir $q_e = \frac{q_{\max} K_L C_e}{1 + K_L C_e}$	$q_{\max} = 15.152$ mg/g $K_L = 44$ mg/L $R^2 = 0.886$	$q_{\max} = 17.24$ mg/g $K_L = 44$ mg/L $R^2 = 0.865$	$q_{\max} = 16.67$ mg/g $K_L = 44$ mg/L $R^2 = 0.911$	$q_{\max} = 16.385$ mg/g $K_L = 44$ mg/L $R^2 = 0.964$
Freundlich $q_F = K_F C_e^{1/n}$	$K_F = 13.985$ $n = 7.246$ $R^2 = 0.877$	$K_F = 14.83$ $n = 6.944$ $R^2 = 0.843$	$K_F = 18.67$ $n = 5.55$ $R^2 = 0.905$	$K_F = 34.64$ $n = 4.18$ $R^2 = 0.955$

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Determination of exponents and constants as used in the empirical model :

Power law equations have been used for the empirical modelling to represent the removal of MB dye as a function of various input parameters. The values of the exponents α , β , γ , δ , λ as shown in eq. (3) have been calculated using non-linear regression analysis both for NSS and HTSS, and shown in Table 4. The values of key variable as shown in eq. (4) have been found by minimizing mean square error and shown in Table 4. The lower values of mean square error for both NSS and HTSS indicate good fitting of experimental data to the proposed empirical model equation^{36,37}.

Table 4. Values of constants and exponents as used in empirical modelling			
Shale	Exponents	Key parameters (κ)	Root Mean Square Error (RMSE)
NSS	$\alpha = -0.079$	0.8898	0.0177
	$\beta = 0.0435$		
	$\gamma = -0.0812$		
	$\delta = 0.0903$		
	$\lambda = 0.0269$		
HTSS	$\alpha = -0.0625$	0.8902	0.0235
	$\beta = -0.0539$		
	$\gamma = -0.0741$		
	$\delta = -0.048$		
	$\lambda = -0.036$		

The empirical model for MB dye removal using NSS and HTSS can be represented as follows :

$$R^* = 0.8898 \times (C^*)^{-0.079} \times (D^*)^{0.0435} \times (S^*)^{-0.0812} \times (T^*)^{0.0903} \times (\theta^*)^{0.0269} \quad (8)$$

$$R^* = 0.8902 \times (C^*)^{-0.625} \times (D^*)^{0.0536} \times (S^*)^{-0.0741} \times (T^*)^{0.048} \times (\theta^*)^{0.036} \quad (9)$$

Effect of initial concentration of MB dye :

From both the eqs. (8) and (9), it has been seen that initial concentration has negative exponent which signifies that removal of dye and initial concentration of dye are inversely related. As initial concentration of dye increases, removal of dye decreases. This is

expected when the process is kinetically driven and not by mass transfer resistance controlled. Literature shows the same^{4,22,24,25}.

Effect of adsorbent dose :

The model represents that increase in adsorbent dose gives higher removal of dye. The ratio of the surface of the adsorbent to the dye molecule increases with increase in adsorbent dose, thereby higher removal occurs^{28,38}. The probability of unoccupied sites increases with increase in adsorbent dose leads to higher dye removal^{29,30}.

Effect of particle size :

Negative exponent on particle size in eqs. (8) and (9) represents the inverse relationship between removal of dye and particle size. It is seen that as the particle size is decreased, removal of dye increases. Lower the particle size, higher will be the surface area for adsorption which results in the higher removal of dye^{4,27,38}.

Effect of temperature :

Positive exponent on temperature in eqs. (8) and (9) indicates direct relationship between removal of dye and temperature. From the kinetic study it has been observed that the removal is almost independent on the temperature under the present range studied. It is evident that diffusion of dye increases with temperature which leads to increase in percentage removal of dye^{31,32}.

Effect of contact time :

It is evident from the eqs. (8) and (9), the response increases with increase in time. This will happen until equilibrium is reached.

From the above discussion it is evident that the developed model is able to predict the functional relations between removal of dye and input variables. To validate the predicted model, maximum, minimum and average errors have been calculated and listed in Table 5. The lower values of average error confirm the applicability of the proposed empirical model to predict removal of dye using shale.

Table 5. Performance of the regression model

Shale	Minimum error (%)	Average error (%)	Maximum error (%)
NSS	0.012	0.139	3.22
HTSS	0.040	0.122	6.61

Experimental

Collection and preparation of shale :

Shale was collected in the form of solid rock from Sonepurbazari coalfield (Latitude : 23°40'06" N and Longitude : 87°11'42" E), Raniganj, West Bengal, India. Shale was initially crushed in Jaw Crusher, followed by grinding in Ball Mill to get finer particles, and it was then sieved to get required particle size. Two forms of shale namely, native and heat treated shales were used for removal of methylene blue. Heat treatment was done by heating the natural shale in a Muffle furnace at 550°C for 1 h. The shale samples were termed as Native Sonepurbazari Shale (NSS) and Heat Treated Sonepurbazari Shale (HTSS).

Studies on characteristics of shale :

Both native and heat treated shale samples were characterized by their bulk density, solid density, moisture content, TOC (total organic carbon), pH_{pzc} , and BET surface area using standard protocol^{21,39-41}. BET surface area was analysed using BET surface area analyser (Quantachrome make Nova 4000e, USA). Simulated solution of methylene blue (100 mg/L) was contacted with NSS (10 g/L) in a batch contactor. After one hour, the solid was separated from solution by centrifugation and kept in an air oven (UNIVERSAL HOT AIR OVEN, India) overnight at 60°C. Thus, the methylene blue loaded sample was prepared and was used for characterization studies. SEM (Scanning Electron Microscopy) studies of native shale samples, with and without MB loading, were done to attain their morphological/geographical characteristics. Scanning Electron Microscope (JEOL JSM-6700 FE, Tokyo) was used for taking photo at desired magnification. Energy Dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) analyses of native shale samples, both with and without methylene blue loading, were done to obtain the compositional variations of the samples

at desired conditions using Energy Dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (JEOL JSM-6700 FE, Tokyo). Fourier Transformation Infrared (FTIR) analysis study was done using FTIR spectrophotometer (Model No. Nicolet iS10, Manufacturer : Thermo Fischer Scientific, USA), for the determination of the functional groups present with their stretching frequencies before and after treatment with methylene blue.

Removal of methylene blue using shale :

Kinetic study :

Stock solution (500 mg/L) of methylene blue (MB) was prepared by dissolving 0.5 g of methylene blue (Merck India Ltd.) in 1.0 L of deionized water. Working solutions of MB dye were made from the above solution by adding definite amount of deionized water. Kinetic study for the removal of MB solution was done using both the native and heat treated shale samples of specific weight and specific particle size in batch mode. The volume of solution, shaking speed and pH were maintained at 50 mL, 150 rpm and 7, respectively in each case. The flasks were kept in BOD Incubator-Shaker (Modern Instrument, India) at a shaking speed of 150 rpm for 10 min at 30°C. The variables such as initial concentration of the methylene blue dye (100–200 mg/L), adsorbent dose (4–12 g/L), size of shale (90–212 μ) and temperature (25–35°C) were varied in prescribed manner. One factor at a time (OFAT) analysis which denotes the changing of one parameter keeping others constant was followed for such purpose. The samples were collected after particular time intervals (0, 2, 4, 6, 8 and 10 min respectively). The collected samples were then centrifuged at 6000 rpm for 10 min. The supernatant was analysed for residual methylene blue concentration using UV-VIS-Spectrophotometer (UV-2300, TECHCOM) at a wavelength of 660 nm.

Equilibrium study :

Methylene blue solutions having concentration in the range of 50 to 200 mg/L were used for equilibrium study. Amount of native shale and volume of solution were maintained as 4 g/L and 50 mL, respectively during the study. Flasks were placed in a BOD Incubator-Shaker and shaken at 150 rpm for 10

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min. Equilibrium study was performed at four different temperatures such as 25, 30, 35 and 40°C. Finally the solutions were centrifuged at 6000 rpm for 10 min and analysed for methylene blue concentration.

Desorption study :

To assess the applicability of the process, desorption study with spent shale was performed. To prepare spent adsorbent, 4 g/L of native shale was contacted with 50 mL of 100 mg/L methylene blue solution for 10 min in BOD-Incubator-Shaker. The slurry was centrifuged at 6000 rpm for 10 min and the solid, thus, obtained is termed as spent shale and used for desorption study. Spent shale (4 g/L) was contacted with three different solutions having pH 3.7, 7.5 and 10 separately for 50 min in BOD-Incubator-Shaker at 30°C. The slurry was centrifuged and the supernatant was analysed for methylene blue concentration.

Empirical modelling :

To analyse the outcome of the input variables on the adsorption of MB dye, an empirical model has been developed. The framing of theoretical model to predict the time variation of response as a function of different input constraints such as adsorbent dose, initial concentration, particle size and temperature is rather difficult, therefore, an empirical model is recommended. In this study an effort has been made to develop an empirical model to analyse the effect of input variables on removal of dye using both NSS and HTSS based on experimental data.

Initially, the removal of dye is expressed as a function of different input parameters

$$R = f(C, D, S, T, \theta) \quad (10)$$

where C = initial concentration of MB dye (mg L^{-1}), D = adsorbent dose (g/L), S = particle size (μ), T = temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$), θ = time (min) and R = percentage removal of MB dye (%).

Assuming Power Law forms of equation, the output variable can be expressed as follows^{36,37} :

$$R = \phi C^{\alpha} D^{\beta} S^{\gamma} T^{\delta} \theta^{\lambda} \quad (11)$$

To get the non-dimensional form of the above equation, the following non-dimensional variables have been used.

$$C^* = \frac{C}{C_{\max}} ; D^* = \frac{D}{D_{\max}} ; S^* = \frac{S}{S_{\max}} ;$$

$$T^* = \frac{T}{T_{\max}} ; \theta^* = \frac{\theta}{\theta_{\max}} ; R^* = \frac{R}{R_{\max}}$$

where C_{\max} = maximum initial concentration of MB dye (mg/L), D_{\max} = maximum adsorbent dose (g/L), S_{\max} = maximum particle size (μ), T_{\max} = maximum temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$), θ_{\max} = maximum time (min), R_{\max} = maximum percentage removal of MB dye (%). The corresponding non-dimensional forms of the above equation is as follows.

$$R^* = \kappa C^{*\alpha} D^{*\beta} S^{*\gamma} T^{*\delta} \theta^{*\lambda} \quad (12)$$

where

$$\kappa = \frac{\phi C_{\max}^{\alpha} D_{\max}^{\beta} S_{\max}^{\gamma} T_{\max}^{\delta} \theta_{\max}^{\lambda}}{R_{\max}} \quad (13)$$

The values of C_{\max} , D_{\max} , S_{\max} , T_{\max} , θ_{\max} , R_{\max} , are 200 mg/L , 12 g L^{-1} , 212 μ , 35 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, 10 min 98.66% and 200 mg/L , 12 g L^{-1} , 212 μ , 35 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, 10 min, 88.90% for both NSS and HTSS, respectively. All the constants and exponents are calculated by non-linear regression method using the experimental data obtained from kinetic study^{36,37}.

Conclusions

Shale, a solid mine waste, has been collected from Sonepurbazari coalfield, Raniganj, West Bengal, India. Both native and heat treated shale have been used for removal of MB dye. Kinetic study was performed to compare their efficacy by varying four variables namely initial concentration, dose of adsorbent, size of adsorbent and temperature. Native shale has been found to be more effective in removal of dye than its heat treated form. Maximum removal (98.66%) has been achieved when 100 mg/L of 50 mL MB solution has been contacted with 12 g/L of NSS at a temperature of 30°C. PSOM and Langmuir adsorption models have been found to be the best to analyse the kinetic and equilibrium data, respectively. An empirical model has been developed to elucidate the functional relationship between percentage removal of dye and input variables. The lower values of average er-

ror confirms suitability of the model. Finally it can be concluded that, shale, the mine waste, can efficiently be used to remove dye from industrial effluent. However, a continuous study encompassing all the parametric effects has to be done for application in industrial scale.

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